

T.C.

BAHCESEHIR UNIVERSITY

GRADUATE SCHOOL OF EDUCATION

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER ENGINEERING

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**ASSESSING ACCESSIBILITY FOR THE ELDERLY WITH VISUAL
IMPAIRMENTS BOTH IN WEB AND MOBILE PLATFORMS: CASE
STUDY**

MASTER'S THESIS

TOGHRUL RAJABLI

BAU 2023

ISTANBUL 2023

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MASTER THESIS APPROVAL FORM

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Student's Name and Surname:	Toghrul Rajabli
Name of The Thesis:	Assessing Accessibility For The Elderly With Visual Impairments Both In Web And Mobile Platforms: Case Study
Thesis Defense Date:	03/07/2023

This thesis has been approved by the Graduate School which has fulfilled the necessary conditions as Master thesis.

.....

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ABSTRACT

ASSESSING ACCESSIBILITY FOR THE ELDERLY WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS BOTH IN WEB AND MOBILE PLATFORMS: CASE STUDY

Toghrul Rajabli

Master's Program in Information Technologies

Thesis Supervisor: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Yücel Batu Salman

June 2023, 55 pages

Web and mobile accessibility play a significant role in guaranteeing that services are equally accessed by people with disabilities, specifically older adults with age related incapacities. The aim of this research is to assess accessibility for elderly with low vision on web and mobile platforms. The study examines the effectiveness of several accessibility strategies, including text resizing, contrast adjustments, text-to-speech functionality, and language controlling. Accessibility principles and guidelines, common barriers and their proper solutions were declared as well. As a case study, we evaluated selected apps on our target groups to enhance accessibility by using latest guidelines. Additionally, combination of heuristic and accessibility evaluation methods were included. After evaluation, a new progressive web app has been created to show possible enhancement towards web and mobile accessibility.

The research findings contribute to accessibility on web and mobile. By using combination of evaluation techniques, proper suggestions were introduced for enhancing accessibility. For creating an accessible app for end users in a proper way, prototypes were designed, then feedbacks were collected from UX experts to those prototypes. The main significance of this research is understanding deeper concepts, enhancing usability, anticipation of practical guidelines, raising awareness and advancement of knowledge regarding web and mobile accessibility.

Keywords: Web and Mobile Accessibility, Heuristic Evaluation, Case Study, Accessibility Guidelines and Principles.

ÖZ

GÖRME ENGELLİ YAŞLILAR İÇİN ERİŞİLEBİLİRLİĞİNİN HEM WEB HEM MOBİL PLATFORMLARDA DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ: VAKA ÇALIŞMASI

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Bilgi Teknolojileri Yüksek Lisans Programı

Tez danışmanı: Doç. Dr. Yücel Batu Salman

Haziran 2023, 55 sayfa

Web ve mobil erişilebilirlik, hizmetlere engelli kişilerin, özellikle yaşa bağlı yetersizlikleri olan yaşlı yetişkinlerin eşit şekilde erişmesini garanti etmede önemli bir rol oynamaktadır. Bu araştırmanın amacı, az gören yaşlılar için web ve mobil platformlarda erişilebilirliğin değerlendirilmesidir. Çalışma, metni boyutlandırma, kontrast ayarlamaları, metinden konuşmaya işlevselliği ve dil denetimi dahil çeşitli erişilebilirlik stratejilerinin etkinliğini inceliyor. Erişilebilirlik ilke ve yönergeleri, ortak engeller ve uygun çözümleri de açıklandı. Bir vaka çalışması olarak, en son yönergeleri kullanarak erişilebilirliği artırmak için hedef gruplarımızdaki seçili uygulamaları değerlendirdik. Buluşsal ve erişilebilirlik değerlendirme yöntemlerinin kombinasyonu dahil edildi. Web ve mobil erişilebilirliğe yönelik olası iyileştirmeyi göstermek için yeni bir aşamalı web uygulaması oluşturuldu.

Araştırma bulguları web ve mobilde erişilebilirliğe katkıda bulunuyor. Değerlendirme teknikleri bir arada kullanılarak erişilebilirliği artırmaya yönelik uygun öneriler getirilmiştir. Son kullanıcılara uygun bir şekilde erişilebilir bir uygulama oluşturmak için prototipler tasarlandı ve ardından bu prototipler için UX uzmanlarından geri bildirimler toplandı. Bu araştırmanın temel önemi, daha derin kavramları anlamak, kullanılabilirliği artırmak, pratik yönergeleri öngörmek, web ve mobil erişilebilirlikle ilgili farkındalığı artırmak ve bilgiyi iletmeğdir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Web ve Mobil Erişilebilirlik, Sezgisel Değerlendirme, Örnek Olay İncelemesi, Erişilebilirlik Yönergeleri ve İlkeleri.

I dedicate this thesis to my family that supported
me throughout my educational life.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I want to thank my supervisor Assoc. Prof. Dr. Yücel Batu Salman from the bottom of my heart for his support, guidance, and advice throughout the thesis.

I would like to thank my parents for their support in my educational life. I would never have been able to pursue this level of education and finish this course without their patience and unwavering support.

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LIST OF ABBRIVIATION

UCD	:	User Centered Design
HCI	:	Human Computer Interaction
UX	:	User Experience
UI	:	User Interface
IA	:	Information Architecture
PM	:	Project Management
ID	:	Interactive Design
HCD	:	Human Centered Design
CS	:	Computer Science
SE	:	Software Engineering
W3C	:	World Web Consortium
WCAG	:	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WAI	:	Web Application Initiatives
AWA	:	Accessibility for Web Applications
UUAG	:	User Agent Accessibility Guidelines
ATAG	:	Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines
WHO	:	World Health Organization

Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, accessibility is a crucial part of people who have some disabilities, such as cognitive, speech, visual, etc. Technologies grow day-by-day; therefore, we should be aware that these people will have difficulties while using modern technology related software and applications. Most of the tech companies do not consider accessibility as a priority in their development phase, and it considers at the final phase of development. There are some disabilities that come related to aging declines, such as vision, cognitive, physical, motor, etc. In our research, we conducted accessibility for elderly people with low vision.

The main purpose of this study is identifying and suggesting practical solutions for accessibility barriers by using WCAG 2.2. Even though our main goal is accessibility, usability, user experience and human computer interaction were presented in our research to understand accessibility deeply. As a research question, accessibility addressed and common barriers, ongoing guidelines, evaluation techniques and tools were discussed based on web and mobile. The main specific target group is elderly people with low vision.

Potential difference and significance of this study is understanding usability and accessibility deeply and suggesting viable solutions on web and mobile by using latest guidelines. Using PWAs by combining heuristic and accessibility evaluation methods is a significance of this study to evaluate accessibility and find accessibility barriers.

While evaluation, both heuristic and accessibility evaluation methodologies were used. Based on most of the research, heuristic, cognitive walkthrough, and accessibility evaluation are main backbone of accessibility. For heuristic evaluation, news related applications were chosen. On the other hand, for accessibility evaluation that UX expert should be part of this research to identify barriers and suggest viable solutions for it, News4Elderly have been created. During evaluation phase of these apps, we were stayed connected with elderly people and gathered data from them.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Nowadays, technological devices and systems grow day-by-day, and companies should be aware of the design of their systems in terms of UI and UX, because they give them usability, accessibility, usefulness etc. Due to these kinds of principles, Interaction Design method has been created, and it consists of several types of sub areas. Interactive Design gives opportunity for any kind of technological product to help people for communicating with them in their daily life. Interactive design helps other kinds of scientific areas to enhance usability and accessibility. These are the areas that Interactive Design takes place in them:

- Computer Science,
- Human-Computer Interaction,
- Human Factors,
- Software Engineering,
- Graphic Design,
- Film Industry,
- Cognitive Engineering, etc.

Interactive Design has a wider range of UX/UI focuses, however, Human-Computer Interaction as a subfield of Interactive Design, it mainly focuses on usability and accessibility of technological products such as web and mobile applications (Sharp, Rogers, & Preece, 2019).

2.1 Definition of Human-Computer Interaction

HCI or Human-Computer Interaction is a subsection part of Computer Science and ID, and it relies on the interaction between human and UX/UI of the computer in a reliable way (Shu, Xiong, & Fan, 2020). According to the research of Szabo and Hercegfi (2022), HCI was presented in the 20th century, and it mostly appeared with UX part. The main importance and focus of HCI is UX related usability that consists of UCD – User Centered Design, or in the other way it is called HCD – Human

Centered Design. HCI analyses the design of computer related technology to enhance satisfaction, usability, and productivity between computer and human interaction.

In this subsection field of CS and ID, people who are related to HCI job field, they call as User Experience designer, User Interface designer, and Usability Engineer. User Centered Design is a solution of inefficiency design of technology, and it aids companies for creating human related design for people. HCI must satisfy people in terms of their technological needs, more specifically disabled people. In this situation, it uses several UX principles. Based on most famous books and articles, proper interaction design should be smart, trustworthy, fit, and clear. Even though there are lots of specifications that must be put into HCI, most of the companies tend to pay attention to commercial points of technologies. Therefore, the main purpose of the HCI can lose its role and importance in technologies. So, it causes huge problem in terms of human centered design, and most of the victims of this scenario are disabled people. Regarding the research that was conducted by Borthwick, Tomitsch and Gaughwin (2022), they have mentioned that there are lots of technological devices, web, and mobile applications, etc. do not fit people who have some disabilities, such as visual impairment, color blindness, older people with slight visual problems, cognitive and physical problems. Therefore, most global companies should not put design principles and importance in second place. They must be aware that this small-term income should lead to some serious long-term problems.

HCI has its own lifecycle for creating proper systems, technological applications, and products. It consists of five parts, and these parts are put in a figure in the following:

Figure 1: HCI design procedure lifecycle (Vishwarupe, et al., 2022).

In the literature review, target is accessibility and its implementation and evaluation. We will focus on web and mobile accessibility and usability for digital applications as well. HCI plays a key role in this situation, and UX principles should be considered in terms of HCI. Most of the research that relates to HCI is mostly conducted with individuals and their interaction with software systems. As it is mentioned in the research of Kuppusamy and Balaji (2021), through surveying, individuals' opinions and thoughts are principal for improving and testing of accessibility and usability in digital platforms. Therefore, both designers and software engineers should be aware of the main UX principles and specifically the main guidelines of web and mobile accessibility, such as WCAG guidelines. HCI is a general and deep concept of user and computers interaction, therefore, it can apply in many areas, which are AI, web and mobile applications development, Software Engineering, etc.

Mobile and web applications develop and deploy day-by-day, and there are some problems occur about accessibility. Nowadays, most designers and software developers do not consider a great deal of accessibility, and this is a problem for people with disabilities. It is mentioned in the article of Paiva, Freire and Forest (2021) that developers should pay attention to universal design principles that relate to accessible design principles and guidelines for disabled people all around the world. However, most of the companies do not obey this rule and they seek the business side of the

product not the usability of them. Therefore, accessibility and usability are important topics these days.

Most of the professors who gained ability in development, were introduced AWA – Accessibility for Web Applications. This is a framework that is an influential guideline for the development steps and process of the web and mobile applications in terms of accessibility. This method is also used in agile software development procedure. In agile method, there are a lot of story cards uses, and they hold main functionalities and designs of web applications. Therefore, UCD and AWA methods are crucial principles in accessibility and usability. According to the research that have been conducted by Miranda and Araujo (2020), agile methodology is one of the most common methodologies about improving usability of a software application in terms of user satisfaction. By using this methodology, it is predictable to improve customer satisfaction, which is crucial for enhancing usability. Beneficial control, flexibility enhancement and continuous improvement towards an application are main benefits of agile methodology.

2.2 User Experience, its principles, and their definitions

As we mentioned before, User Experience or UX plays a key role in HCI, and it supplies user functionality of technologies and how to interpret them. UX pays attention to users about what they need to use and how. Don Norman is an inventor of UX, and he created the way of communication path with product individually and entire experience towards these products (Zardari, Hussain, Arain, Rizvi, & Vighio, 2021). Additionally, User Experience helps companies with their business aims and goals towards a project. According to Jesse James Garrett, every item that has been used by people has user experience. There are tons of areas that linked to UX, and these areas and their principles, which related to HCI procedures identify creating a proper user centered design for people. These are the areas (Usability.gov, 2022):

- IA or Information Architecture: concentrates structure, organization, and presentation of information with the way of accessibility for users,
- UI or User Interface: considers needs of user in terms of interface elements,
- Accessibility: considers people with disabilities and normalize UI/UX of web site, mobile applications, or system to them,

- PM or Project Management: considers planning of a project and resource related to it. In this procedure, UCD applies to the PM team to satisfy users.

According to the research of Knight (2019), there are some misunderstandings about the UX. According to Don Norman who is pioneer of User Experience, sometimes developers and companies misunderstand UX and its principal branches. This leads us to accessibility and usability problems. Therefore, we stuck with them. So, we should look at UX with its detail, and differences about its subfields and branches.

Primarily, UX does not mean UI. UX holds lots of disciplines, such as User Experience Design, Industrial Design, Visual Design, Human Factors, Interaction Design, Human-Computer Interaction, etc. Although it holds lots of principles, UI is just a small piece of mega UX part. These branches have crucial meaning regarding UX goal of business. Therefore, we should pick one of them and develop a system based on our goal. As a conclusion of first part, different goals mean different principles.

Secondly, Knight also mentioned that UX is not just a usability for systems and technological products. When considering usability, the straightforward way of using products comes to mind first. However, many tech companies misunderstand this concept unfortunately. Developers must think of a broader point of view, not just thinking whether a product is usable or not, because usability on a part of UX.

Finally, UX is not only about consumer or user. Users and their needs are appraised in the User Centered Design section that is a special sub-section of HCI. While thinking about the user, we must not put UX in the same phase.

For understanding UX and its goal, especially usability, we must look its principles. These are the principles in the following (Knight, 2019):

- Useful – developed applications must be right for users’ needs, and it should solve their problems,
- Usable – developed applications should be easy to use and learn. Good UI design and UXD must be included in applications,

- Findable – users can easily find things that they need and use in developed applications,
- Credible – developed application must be reliable,
- Accessible – developed applications should be relevant to all people, specifically for disabled people,
- Desirable – developed applications should link to a major brand to supply better experience to users,
- Valuable – besides users, developed applications should present a value for shareholders as well.

The list of these principles is also called Peter Morville’s UX Honeycomb.

Figure 2: Peter Morville’s UX honeycomb (Usability.gov, 2022).

2.2.1 Implementation of UX and integration into software development. In this section, we will introduce the implementation UX, and integration into any kind of developed software programs. Before we dive into implementation and integration, we must be aware that implementation and integration are not easy duties and achievements that we can accomplish. Most of the software companies try to implement and integrate UX after development phase of the products, or in other words, applications. However, we need to implement UX with their relevant methods

that differ from the goal of one software company to another and integrate them into our software while in development processes. In the research of Cajander, Larusdottir and Geiser (2022), while implementation phase, we should list implementation methods, but for the integration, we must put them into our software. So, principles and practices of UX must be modified and placed by putting into previously built software development methods and applications.

While integrating usability, the same scenario occurs in software development. Some of the challenges that companies face to. Challenges differ from one development procedure or scenario to another. One of the most crucial challenges and difficulties is usability. Usability is a part of User Experience and core principle of it. However, when we define UX, we should not consider only usability perspective (Trukenbrod, Backhaus, & Thomaschke, 2020). According to the research of Kashfi, Feldt and Nilsson (2019), there are distinctive qualities of UX that separate it from usability, such as partisanship (mainly depend on user insights), vigorous (transformations a lot over time), meaningful (embraces profound outcomes of consuming), and framework-associated (linked to the context).

There are some challenges that software developers would be aware of while integrating UX to their software products. First, lifelong studying is the key concept for every single UX senior that produces an accessibility and usability perspective for new technology. Hence UX seniors should use new UX methods in their work, lifelong study makes them learn every new detail in innovative technologies. Many UX methods arise in lifelong learning situations. Lifelong learning or studying is a term that is related to nonstop studying of abilities, achieving experience, and applying it to new developed and different fields (Geiser, 2020). Based on the research of Cajander, Larusdottir and Geiser (2022), UX knowledge of current technology has a life of about 2-3 years, and it means that, after 2-3 years the current knowledge will be obsolete. So, this is another problem that occurs during software development phase in terms of UX seniors and Software Engineers. However, lifelong studying makes UX seniors and Software Engineers anxious while keeping up to date their knowledge towards their proficiency fields.

Regarding the study that was driven by Ferati and Vogel (2020), most of the software developers and designers are not instructed topic like accessibility in courses such as in Computer Science. They have done a survey at one the universities of Sweden about courses related to the Computer Science. They have gathered data that only 14.3 percent of the total course teach accessibility in their curriculum, which is not enough for software engineers and designers. Therefore, most of the developers have not represented solid knowledge about accessibility and usability in survey as well.

There are lots of UX methods that can integrate to the software development phase, however, these methods can be vague and difficult to software development and its target. Based on the research that have been driven by Bruun, Nielsen, Larusdottir, Nielse and Perrson (2018), the most common method is Agile method that is used in software development, and UX integration as well. Due to development phase may be different in terms of goal and aim, UX methods mean different sense for them. Also, UX methods take lots of time to acquire and apply. Therefore, it is recommended that each software developer and UX professional should use easy and basic methods to their software development phase. These struggles can also raise accessibility and usability problems as well. Besides these methods, there are some methodologies that help UX seniors to evaluate the usability. For example, heuristic evaluation and cognitive walkthrough are main methodologies in terms of evaluating usability. According to the research of Martínez, Ribera and Granollers (2021), heuristic evaluation is the pretty straightforward method for evaluating usability. In that research, they have driven an accessibility evaluation in divergent phases, and heuristic evaluation was used properly. In the conclusion of this research, they have shown that by using heuristic evaluation method, accessibility issues can be easily solved. While using these methodologies, we can evaluate accessibility properly as well, due to the main connection between accessibility and usability

Based on studies such as Nielsen et al., (2018), Geiser (2020), Cajander and Larusdottir (2022) while implementation and integration process of UX, software developers and even UX seniors still have problems about that. Due to shortage of appropriate UX methods, toughness of the seniors' roles and lifelong learning that takes too much time to get around in the up to dated technological world, lead to worse

consequences for software development. According to the research of Travis and Hodgson (2022), while conducting UX reviews based on usability, we should eliminate one user's perspective and reviewer in software development, using common usability principles. For example, Nielsen's heuristics that consists of Error prevention, User control and freedom, Flexibility, and efficiency of use etc. (Aela Design and Training, 2022). Unlike other modern technology related principles, this principle has been in use for more than a decade, and it does not require specific rules for usability to apply.

2.3 Accessibility and Usability

Accessibility is a term that refers to any kind of product that should be usable for many kinds of people who have some disabilities. There are lots of disabilities that make people's life hard, such as blindness, cognitive problems, physical disability, speech related problems, and specifically aging that brings some problems in it such as color blindness, slight visual impairment, etc. In the web and mobile platforms, sometimes accessibility refers to Digital Accessibility. According to WHO or The World Health Organization, there are approximately 1 billion individuals who have some sort of disabilities (World Health Organization, 2021). Therefore, those people should have the same availability to get all kinds of information from digital platforms, as same as normal individual. In the research of Inal, Guribye, Rajanen Dorina and Mikko, and Rost (2020), there are lots of poorly designed websites and mobile applications in terms of accessibility, this is because of the less obligation in some of companies. Some of them, especially UX seniors, do not consider accessibility as a main goal in their software development phase. However, governmental websites and mobile applications that are related to the public services meet the requirements of accessibility to disabled people. Many companies like Apple, Google and Microsoft supply some handy tools for their developers to create accessible and usable products. As an example, their operating systems provide lots of precious tools for people with disabilities, such as visual, hearing, and visual aiding systems. Even though we are in a technological era, we still suffer from accessibility and usability of our technological devices and systems. Why do we get stuck in accessibility first? According to the research of Sharp, Rogers and Preece (2019), the solution for the problem is first,

achieving accessibility by using Interactive Design principles, and most essentially Human-Computer Interaction, second, using usable technology.

We should be aware of diverse kinds of disabilities, while creating and designing accessible technological products. There are several types of disabilities that we should consider, such as sensory, physical, and cognitive disabilities. Different companies have created and developed many kinds of software programs and applications that attribute one of those kinds of disabilities. As an example, Visolve, and Color-Blind Pal are apps for color blind people, Be My Eyes, Cash Reader, Sound Scape, and Smart Magnifier for blind people, Mental UP, Otismo, and 2Talk for cognitive problems. Each of these disabilities holds sub-categorical problems. For example, in visual impairment, there are various kinds of problems, such as color blindness, vision loss due to aging, or total blindness. Also, Sharp et al. (2019) mentioned that based on divergent types of problems, distinctive approaches and methods use. For color blindness and slight visual loss, Interactive Design approach, specifically HCI and UX is enough to overcome this problem. However, for blind people, we should supply assistive tools to use. As we understand these kinds of problems and their approach, we can undertake the accessibility problem easily.

The importance of usability appeared with the popularity of Human-Computer Interaction in UX. Also, usability is defined by ISO 9241-11 that, usability is the degree to that a product may be consumed by targeted users to accomplish clear goals in a particular context of use with efficiency, satisfaction, and effectiveness (ISO 9241-210:2019, 2022). According to the research of Brdnic, Hericko and Sumak (2022), for achieving the intended result in accessibility and usability, effectiveness is a vital principle. User Interface and User Experience Design took usability as a base of the design. In many points of view, usability covers all aspects of the design principles at all, and it clarifies errors, fulfillment, and learnability.

In the research of Iancu Ioana and Bogdan (2020), usability definitions should be clear based on devices to evaluate usability and accessibility. Those definitions adopted from Nielsen's main principles:

- Learnability that does not need any pre planned practice to learn a device,
- Efficiency that is achieving goal in a limited time,

- Memorability is the simplicity of re-learning a gadget after extended periods of inactivity,
- Errors that developers should decrease possible errors for end user,
- Satisfaction that users should be positive towards the device.

These principles are main backbone of usability, and by using these, we can achieve accessibility as well.

Based on the research of Szabo and Hercegfı (2022), in UX, the general analysis of usability and accessibility consists of two kinds of research method categorization. First, analytic method focuses on the usage and activity of users towards technological product of UX. It does not demand any user participation while researching with this method. However, in the empirical method, software applications based on our case should be handed away to users for evaluation. Therefore, empirical methods need the participation of users, careful management, and association in terms of applications. So, heuristic, or cognitive methodology can help us to manage this situation by adding User Centered Design principle.

As a conclusion, we consider both accessibility and usability as major aspects for creating an accessible software application. As a developer or UX senior, we should not differentiate usability and accessibility.

2.3.1 Challenges of accessibility during implementation and evaluation.

Implementation and evaluation of accessibility in terms of an application, sometimes cumbersome and arduous. One of the main difficulties is lack of proper knowledge about one of the specific disabilities for software. Additionally, accessibility techniques are not enough to apply, because of a variety of accessibility problems and scenarios. In the research of Bi, Xia, Lo, Grundy, Zimmermann, and Ford (2022), web and mobile accessibility and usability were introduced, and HCI and SE were emphasized for defining them. For the accessibility part, most of the disabilities, specifically visual impairments in terms of older people, were discussed. However, the main idea was practitioners practice and their attitude towards web accessibility and usability. They were put in a questionnaire and taken survey. Software projects perspective in terms of accessibility has been discussed. Due to inefficient clearness of the accessibility features for current software, there are gaps between the

accessibility and software implementation. There are some issues supporting this problem such as inadequate feedback and usability. Also, Human Computer Interaction and Software Engineering communities suggest that accessibility should apply in development phase, not the end of the development. According to a conclusion of research, around fifty percent of SE suffers from implementing accessibility in development. Based on interview questionnaires, SE focuses on low vision, color blindness and hearing issues while programming, design, management, and testing of software.

The main challenges of accessibility during implementation and evaluation, inefficient feedback from users, lack of expertise, hardness of accessibility and usability principles.

However, automatic evaluation tools are a shortcut for decreasing time and money consuming while implementation and evaluation. According to the result of the research of Pelzetter (2021), there are various kinds of evaluation tools that work on either web or mobile platforms. Both have cons and pros, and they cannot check all inefficiencies. Even though some of them have abundant amounts of documentation and sources, most of the time it is hard to pay attention to all of them and understand. The most demanded tools are A-Tester, Mauve, WAVE for web, and DigitalA11Y and TPGi for mobile applications. As mentioned, there are lots of tools to use, but some of them address properly and accurately. Therefore, choosing one of these tools is crucial as well. According to the research that was driven by Ismailova and Inal (2022), Mauve and Cynthia Says are precise to detect errors about accessibility. In the research, various kinds of tools were used while checking governmental websites from all over the world. As an example, AChecker, Mauve, Cynthia Says, Access Monitor, etc. According to the results of these tools, Mauve and Cynthia Says detected more accessibility errors than others based on WCAG levels that are A, AA, and AAA.

According to the accessibility evaluation discussion of Acosta-Varga, Salvador-Acosta, Zalakeviciute and Alexandrino (2020), there are some phases we should follow:

- Choose app,
- Consider target group,

- Listing difficulties for the group,
- Making a test drive setting,
- Using auto-evaluator tools for checking the accessibility of the app,
- Paying attention to the listed barriers carefully,
- Storing and analyzing of the outcomes,
- Proposing enhancements towards accessibility.

2.3.2 Challenges of accessibility guidelines and standards. Based on our research its noticed that not only implementation of accessibility while developing of web and mobile applications is a unique problem, the hardiness of Guidelines and Standards and evaluation of accessibility are other challenges that we face to. Based on the research of Vollenwyder, Opwis and Brühlmann (2020), one of the disadvantages of the WCAG is the guideline based on English language. Even though W3C made some improvements about translations of the guidelines in various kinds of languages, some languages are missing, such as Turkish, Azerbaijani, etc. Another challenge is obscurity of words and jargon, which even developer can hardly understand, and these problems lead to misunderstandings. Therefore, developers can easily get frustrated in this situation. Also, the guideline alone does not mean accessibility perfection at all and improving accessibility needs money and time.

Furthermore, there are some web sites that aid developers to get enough information about accessibility and usability. Based on the research of Gaggi and Perinello (2022), a case study has been conducted by using MyWcag4All website that is about accessibility tools that is referenced to WCAG 2.1. The web site offers lots of tools for checking accessibility. User Interface of the website is user friendly and there is a filter that sorts all the accessibility tools out that should be considered while implementing accessibility to applications. Instead of listing complex guideline principles, this web site listed all the tools that developers need and easily apply to their applications. According to the results of the case study, most of the developers claimed this solution is neutral and useful based on understandability of instruction, UI friendliness and intuition of the web site.

As a conclusion of this section, accessibility, either mobile or web, should be understood as an important part of any digital product. For enhancing the accessibility,

we must enthusiastically speak with the predefined groups of people for their specific needs. Software engineers must consider accessibility as an important part of their development. Finally, web and mobile accessibility would be recognized as valuable for the excellence of a software product.

2.4 Web and Mobile Accessibility

Mobile accessibility refers to the design and development of mobile applications, and mobile devices to ensure that they are usable by people with disabilities. The main goal of mobile accessibility is to provide equal access and equal opportunity to people with disabilities to use and benefit from mobile technologies. The significance of mobile devices in terms of their universal applicability has greatly expanded the market for mobile applications (Yang & Lin, 2019). Based on the research of Mateus, Silva, Oliveira, Costa and Freire (2021), mobile accessibility principles are based on the concept of universal design, which means that products and technologies should be designed in a way that makes them usable by as many people as possible, regardless of their abilities, disabilities, or age.

As mobile accessibility, web accessibility considers the accessibility of web applications, websites, and their design for people with disabilities. Web accessibility has been practicing and enhancing for a long time than mobile accessibility has done. Based on the research of Leite, Scatalon, Freire and Eler (2021), since the World Wide Web has grown into the most frequently used platform for organizations to share information and provide many of their services, web accessibility is arguably the most known example of digital accessibility. However, there is also a current push on mobile accessibility, particularly considering the growing popularity of mobile platforms and the difficulties associated with using mobile devices for human input due to their small screens, wide range of hardware and software configurations, complex user interfaces, and other factors. According to the research of Alajarmeh (2021), there are lots of guidelines that are implemented to web and mobile accessibility. WCAG is the most popular accessibility guidelines that support both web and mobile platforms. Moreover, there are some principles that are used while developing web and mobile applications.

Table 1

POUR Principle of WCAG for Mobile and Web Accessibility (Nuñez, Moquillaza, & Paz, 2019):

No	Principle	Definition
1	Perceivable	Information and user interfaces should be presentable to users in ways they can perceive, i.e., through visual, auditory, and touch feedback.
2	Operable	User interfaces should be operable using a keyboard, touch screen, or other assistive technology.
3	Understandable	Information and the function of user interfaces should be understandable.
4	Robust	Content should be robust enough that it can be interpreted by a wide variety of user instruments, such as assistive technologies.

Each of these principles has its amounts of success criteria based on WCAG. Perceivable principle holds 22 success criteria, operable principle 20, understandable 17, and robust 2 success criteria (Park, So, & Cha, 2019).

The guidelines for mobile accessibility are based on the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines or WCAG 2.1/2.2, that is a widely recognized set of guidelines for making web content accessible. Based on most of the research, such as (Yang & Lin, 2019), (Lin & Ho, 2020), (Zhang, et al., 2021) and (Mateus, Silva, Oliveira, Costa, & Freire, 2021) the guidelines for mobile accessibility include the following:

1. Provide alternative text for images and other non-text content.

2. Use a large enough font size and provide sufficient contrast between text and background.
3. Use meaningful headings and structure content using lists, tables, and other appropriate structures.
4. Provide clear and concise instructions and feedback to users.
5. Allow users to control the time limits for content, such as video and audio playback.
6. Make sure that users can navigate the content using a keyboard and touch screen.
7. Provide audio descriptions and captions for video content.
8. Ensure that users can zoom in on content without losing content or functionality.
9. Ensure that users can turn off animations and flashing content.
10. Supply text descriptions for graphs and charts.

Mobile accessibility and web accessibility are an important consideration for the design and development of mobile applications, websites, and mobile devices. By following the principles and guidelines for mobile accessibility, designers and developers can ensure that their products are usable by as many people as possible, including those with disabilities. Ensuring that mobile technologies are accessible to everyone is not only a legal requirement but also a moral imperative, as it helps to ensure that everyone has equal access and equal opportunity to the benefits that mobile technologies offer.

2.4.1 Web and mobile accessibility evaluation methods. While evaluating accessibility in both web and mobile platforms, developers and designers use various kinds of evaluation methods. It is not obligatory to use all of them, however, combining them as a guideline to evaluate can give better results to learn accessibility barriers and suggestions for them to enhance application usability of elderly people. While exploring articles related to methods for evaluation of accessibility, various kinds of research have been done by various kinds of people all over the world. Many researchers prefer to use multiple types of evaluation methods such as user participation, expert evaluation, and automation tools. In the study that was conducted by Nuñez, Moquillaza and Paz (2019), they have applied a systematic literature review

about accessibility evaluation methods. According to the findings and analysis, the most effective methods are user and expert participation. Sometimes automation tools could not provide proper solutions for accessibility. However, there are various kinds of effectful evaluation methods that aid to conduct accessibility evaluation properly. For example, heuristic evaluation, cognitive walkthrough, and user centered design. Heuristic evaluation is more like practical rather than cognitive walkthrough, which requires more documentational preparation. While conducting research by using heuristic evaluation method, we should hire at least three or five UX professionals to evaluate usability, additionally, User Centered Design can be beneficial for evaluation of usability.

Although heuristic evaluation considers about usability, we found principles and evaluation techniques for accessibility. Principles are same as the WCAG principles such as perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust. For evaluation techniques:

- Visual inspection
- Keyboard navigation testing
- Screen reader testing
- Color contrast testing
- Alternative text testing.

All these techniques and principles adjacent to WCAG guidelines. While conducting accessibility evaluation research by using heuristic method, we should contact some UX/UI and accessibility experts to evaluate selected web or mobile apps as well as applicability of research methods. Before starting a heuristic evaluation for accessibility, we should draw up a proper plan that includes scope of the research, targeted groups, selected applications, and relevant accessibility guidelines. The best practice for accessibility evaluation is combining heuristic evaluation with case study. Regarding the research of Acosta-Vargas et al. (2020), accessibility barriers were identified by using heuristic evaluation about mobile application in terms of people with low vision. There are lots of research have been done with heuristic evaluation in the researches of Park, So and Cha (2019) and Alcaraz, Ribera and Ganollers (2021) as well. In the research of Galkute, Rojas and Sagal (2020), various kinds of evaluation

methods were used, but, heuristic evaluation considered the best approach for usability and accessibility, and most of the accessibility errors occur in A and AA levels.

In terms of cognitive walkthrough, we should prepare more documentational related plans such as task scenarios, simulation of UI, identification of usability problems and making recommendations for them.

According to the research of Meurer, Stein, Randall and Wulf (2018), for User Involvement or User Centered Design in terms of accessibility evaluation, participation of people with disabilities, determining the type of evaluation that includes only one or combination of the evaluation methods, test plan and analyzing the results take place. User Centered Design is broad type of evaluation method, and we can use more than one type of distinct evaluation method, while using this methodology.

Additionally, surveying is another preferable methodology to identify errors and barriers. Regarding of the research of Pichiliani and Pizzolato (2021), they have designed an explanatory survey for cognitive disabilities. As a result, they have found that most of the developers do not know about disabilities and accessibility principles.

In the subsequent paragraphs, we will explain about the main accessibility evaluation methods.

2.4.1.1 User participation. While checking and implementing accessibility in both web and mobile platforms, we should involve users in the development phase. The most relevant method for this is User Centered Design methodology. Even though this is one of the costly and time-consuming ways, the results can be awesome and satisfying. In user participation method, developers should make an application scenario to assess it. According to the research of Nuñez, Moquillaza and Paz (2019), one of the important advantages of this method is you can easily and directly find accessibility errors on applications, disability barriers, and perfect solutions for them. However, there are lots of disability factors that we should consider, and this can be challenging to evaluate it. Hence, developers and designers should consider a specific target group, such as low-vision, blindness, cognitive, and mental disabilities. Besides these requirements, the domain of evaluated apps or websites should be declared by

developers and designers. As a domain, we can list lots of areas like information, government, health, etc. Additionally, developers would be knowledgeable regarding accessibility guidelines to evaluate and provide accessibility solutions accurately. Regarding of the case study that was conducted by Acosta-Vargas, Salvador-Ullauri, Perez and Zalakeviciute (2020), heuristic method and accessibility evaluation method were used. Combining with Nielsen's usability evaluation methods and WCAG 2.1 principles, accessibility assessment stages were introduced for evaluating air quality mobile apps. In the study, target group was people with disabilities of visual impairment. As a result, lots of barriers were found and they have suggested that user participation with heuristic evaluation is effectful about evaluation.

2.4.1.2 Automated evaluation instruments. For both web and mobile applications, automated evaluation instruments are solution for accessibility checking. These kinds of tools analyze accessibility of any applications. According to the research of Dias, Carvalho, Rocha, and Barroso (2022), these tools give suggestions based on the inefficiencies about the usability and accessibility. Tools recognize problems by using WCAG guideline, therefore, this is the best less cost effective and time-consuming method to analyze the usability and accessibility. There are lots of tools for checking accessibility such as WAVE, Mauve++, AChecker, etc. All these tools rely on WCAG 2.1 guideline, and they can check single page applications.

However, tools may be limited to checking all errors and suggesting the right solution. For example, while putting an app which is created by using React Native, tool shows some errors that there are not labels for input elements, even though label was declared with separate way. Additionally, tools cannot define whether the labels such as image identifiers are related to the image or not. Due to react and react native libraries use JSX, some kinds of problems can occur in terms of HTML contents. (Mateus, Silva, Oliveira, Costa, & Freire, 2021).

It is recommended to use combination of these methods, such as in the research of Królak and Zajac (2022), they have used automation tool and heuristic method to evaluate accessibility regarding various kinds of disabilities. As a result, the most barriers occur in operable and perceivable principles. Additionally, they have

suggested that heuristic evaluation is recommended to evaluate, finding barriers and accessibility errors.

2.4.1.3 Expert observation. Another money and time-consuming method are expert observation and evaluation. In this method, an expert evaluates the hole scenarios based on his knowledge about WCAG guidelines and suggests solutions. If there are not any scenarios to test, then the expert pays attention to make a case study planning to evaluate accessibility properly.

2.5 W3C Guidelines

World Web Consortium was established in 1994 and it has various kinds of standards and guidelines about accessibility. Governments all over the world have established rules and regulations to make the Web more available for people with disabilities. More than 19 nations contributed to the effective completion of web accessibility. According to the World Wide Web Consortium website's laws and policies, have created their own policies, laws, and legislations (Ismail & Kuppusamy, 2019).

There are lots of accessibility guidelines that we should include in our web and mobile applications. The guidelines that we will talk about are the main structure and base content of accessibility. We cannot think about accessibility without these guidelines on the web and mobile platforms. For serving more available web and mobile apps to disable people, we should aware and implement these guidelines. There is a question that why we should care about accessibility and its guidelines? There are lots of answers for it, but we can answer it with Martin Luther King Jr. quote's that "Injustice anywhere is a threat to justice everywhere..." (King, 1963). If we want to equalize the usability and accessibility of web and mobile contents for everyone and including disable people, we should stick to the accessibility principles.

2.5.1 Web content accessibility guideline. WCAG or Web Content Accessibility Guideline is a pragmatic standard and guideline for developing accessible and usable web and mobile content for people with some disabilities. WCAG was developed by World Web Consortium. WCAG shows general errors and bugs in web and even mobile contents in terms of accessibility. However, WCAG do not totally identify techniques in its documentation that which one of them is the best

solution and successful criteria for accessibility. There are lots of scenarios, and therefore, for the evaluation and implementation of accessibility, developers and designers should pay careful attention to the details and scenarios to produce some success factors for accessibility and usability. There are plenty of WCAG versions such as WCAG 2.0, 2.1, and 2.2 which will be completed in early 2023, but WCAG 2.0 and 2.1 are used in web and mobile content. WCAG 2.1 holds seventeen new standards for people with low vision and cognitive disabilities. Success criteria related to AAA level for every website. Level A has the smallest requirements, AA holds enough requirements that every organization should obey this level and superior level AAA (Dias, Carvalho, Rocha, & Barroso, 2022). Based on success criteria for AA level, WCAG 2.0 holds 38, WCAG 2.1 contains 50 and WCAG 2.2 contains 57 success criteria. In terms of total success criteria, which contains A, AA, and AAA level, WCAG 2.0 holds 61 and WCAG 2.1 holds 78 success criteria and principle (Campoverde-Molina, Lujan-Mora, & Garcia, 2020), (Filipe, Pires, & Gouveia, 2023). The importance of WCAG 2.2 is improving accessibility for people who have low vision, cognitive disabilities, and incapacities in terms of the usage of mobile platforms. According to the new draft of WCAG 2.2, compared to WCAG 2.1, 9 extra success criteria were added by W3C (W3C, 2022) :

- Focus Not Obscured
- Focus Appearance
- Accessible authentication
- Visible Control
- Page Break Navigation

The whole guideline about WCAG 2.1 and latest WCAG 2.2 are given on the official W3C website. From WCAG 2.0 to the latest WCAG guideline support mobile accessibility. Moreover, standards such as AA level can apply to mobile accessibility. For accessibility testing of all these guidelines, ACT or Accessibility Conformance Testing rule was discovered. The ACT rules are helpful when designing automated testing tools and human testing methodologies because they supply an ordinary understanding of what items the rule is applied to and what checks should be performed automatically and/or manually for each test needed by the WCAG. This

makes testing procedures transparent and consistent, including those used by accessibility testing tools. This is because not only are the requirements sometimes difficult to understand without extensive knowledge of web technologies, but also because it necessitates looking at a variety of details at once. Accessibility validators, a type of technology, were quickly developed to address such issues (Giovanna, Manca, Paterno, & Pulina, 2020).

In WCAG 2.2, there are lots of success criteria that we should consider for older people with low vision in our case. The research that was conducted by Królak and Zając (2022), WCAG success criteria were listed relevant to their principles and levels. In that research, they have used heuristic methods, user participation and automated evaluation as a methodology to evaluate online courses for people with incapacities. While researching, WCAG success criteria was used with that we can implement in our case study. Different from that, we have identified principles for their success criteria that related to low vision (W3C, 2023):

Table 2

WCAG 2.2 Principles With Their Success Criteria and Levels.

Principle	Success criteria	Level
Perceivable	Non-text context	A
	Audio control	A
	Audio description	A
	Color usage	A
	Resize text	AA
	Text spacing	AA
	Contrast	AAA
Operable	Keyboard	A
	No keyboard traps	A
	Bypass blocks	A
	Heading and labels	AA
	Section headings	AAA
	Link purpose	AAA
Understandable	Language of pages	A
	Error identification	A
	Error suggestions	AA
	Consistent navigation	AA
	Pronunciation	AAA
Robust	Value, roles	A
	Status message	AA

2.5.2 Web application initiative. WAI or Web Application Initiative is a guideline that has established by W3C for suggesting the right way of handling accessibility in web platform. The guideline uses in mobile platforms as well (Paiva, Freire, & Fortes, 2021).

2.5.3 User agent accessibility guidelines. UUAG or User Agent Accessibility Guideline is a guideline that illustrates how browsers and other media players are accessible for consumers (Ferati & Vogel, 2020).

2.5.4 Authoring tool accessibility guidelines. ATAG or Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines holds consumable software for developers and designers to create accessible web content (Ferati & Vogel, 2020).

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

In our research, we have done a case study by using heuristic and accessibility evaluation methodologies. We have analyzed more than fifty online resources for HCI, UX/UI design principles, and especially for accessibility and usability in the last five years. The main idea is accessibility in web and mobile platforms, however, for getting deeper information related to this area, we had to explore broad topics such as HCI and UX. We also created an accessible PWA app based on data that we have explored and feedback that we collected from UX experts. We assigned scenarios to elderly people to check usability as well.

While conducting this research, we have used more than fifty online resources from various websites such as Google scholar, Springer, ScienceDirect, IEEE explore, Scopus, MDPI, ACM Digital Library, John Benjamins e-platform, Frontiers and Semantic Scholar. For choosing relevant research articles, we have used words that relate to our purpose. Considering search strategy, we have chosen words carefully while researching.

Table 3

States that We Have Used While Researching.

No	State
1	("web accessibility" OR "accessibility in web platform")
2	("web accessibility evaluation" OR "web evaluation for elderly")
3	("web application" OR "web page" OR "website")
4	("accessibility evaluation on web") ("automated evaluation tool for web applications")
5	("web usability" OR "web usability for elderly")
6	("mobile accessibility" OR "accessibility in mobile platform")
7	("mobile accessibility evaluation" OR "mobile evaluation for elderly")
8	("automated evaluation tool for mobile applications")
9	("mobile usability" OR "mobile usability for elderly")
10	("accessibility for elderly people" OR "web accessibility for older people" OR "mobile accessibility for older people")
11	("human computer interaction" OR "HCI")
12	("UX" OR "user experience")
13	("UX methods" OR "UX techniques")

Table 4

Research Questions

No	Research Questions	References
1	Which accessibility evaluation techniques and tools were emphasized in the literature review?	(Nuñez, Moquillaza, & Paz, 2019)
2	What are the main barriers for elderly people while using mobile and web apps?	(Pichiliani & Pizzolato, 2021)
3	What are the ongoing and main guidelines for supporting accessibility in web and mobile?	(Paiva, Freire, & Fortes, 2021)
4	Which methodology is appropriate for evaluating accessibility?	(Alcaraz, Ribera, & Granollers, 2021), (Park, So, & Cha, 2019) and (Acosta-Vargas, Salvador-Acosta, Zalakeviciute, & Alexandrino, 2020)

3.2 Setting and Target Participants

Accessibility covers various kinds of disabilities, however, for the sake of our research, we have identified older people with low vision. In our research, we have reached out to elderly people to get feedback about our app and give them an opportunity to enhance the accessibility problem. The main reason behind this is increasing accessibility in web and mobile platforms. Our main goal is to find out barriers and challenges of accessibility and improve it by using WCAG 2.2 guidelines. Based on our observations, we have recorded their experience in the usage of web and

mobile applications. For policy issues, we have declared nicknames instead of their names in our research anonymously.

Table 5

Participant with Their Nicknames, Genders, Ages, and Types of Disabilities

ID	Nickname	Gender	Age	Types of disabilities
1	P1	Male	65	Low vision
2	P2	Female	65	Low vision
3	P3	Female	62	Low vision
4	P4	Male	63	Low vision
5	P5	Male	70	Low vision
6	P6	Female	63	Low vision

In table 5, we have identified older people with low vision by adding their age, gender and nicknames. Some of our participants are adventurous about finding something related to technology as an innovation. While keeping in touch those participants, they have warmly welcomed accessibility enhancement for our research.

Table 6

Years of Desktop and Smartphone Usage of Participants

Participants	Years of desktop use	Years of smartphone use
P1	8	10
P2	<1	5
P3	3	4
P4	2	4
P5	2	5
P6	<1	4

In table 6, years of mobile and desktop use were described for each of the participants.

3.3 Procedures

3.3.1 Data collection instruments. In this section, we will introduce data collection instruments that we have used in our research. We conducted a case study by implementing heuristic evaluation with specific target group that consisted of elderly people. Based on our research of various kinds of articles, we have come up with some questions. We gathered relevant data from our created app that contains some WCAG 2.2 principles for low vision people. Our app that is called News4Elderly, is a public Progressive Web App that adapts to web and mobile platforms. Next.js, React.js and Node.js were used in the app. According to the research of Roumeliotis and Tselikas (2022), there are lots of advantages of using PWAs, such as accessibility of apps, offline usage, fast loading, reliability, cross-platform and installable. Installable is a feature of a PWA that a user does not need to download the app from any store and use it on home screen without opening browser repeatedly. Additionally, with cache functionality, users can consume apps offline after fetching data from an API.

While developing our app, we involved user in development phase as accessibility evaluation method. Our app is being analyzed by UX experts as well. Additionally, for the case study, we have evaluated most popular and demanding apps that are cross platform and accessible as well. Both the combination of accessibility evaluation and heuristic evaluation can give us broad understanding and finding for accessibility in web and mobile.

Table 7

Applications with Their Links and Compatibility Platforms

Id	App	Links	Compatible platforms
1	BBC News Azerbaijan	https://www.bbc.com/azeri	Web and mobile
2	Metbuat	https://metbuat.az/	Web and mobile
3	Oxu	https://oxu.az/	Web and mobile
4	News4Elderly	https://news4elderly.vercel.app/	Web and mobile

Figure 3: BBC News Azerbaijan on web and mobile.

Figure 4: Metbuat on web and mobile.

Figure 5: Oxu on web and mobile.

These figures represent the view of PWAs on web and mobile platforms. However, we will present our app in findings section.

3.3.2 Data collection procedures. During data collection procedure, heuristic evaluation was used as a case study. Based on most of research, there are some steps for the heuristic evaluation such as choosing app and objective groups, distinguishing app tasks, evaluating barriers, recording, and analyzing results, finally, recommending enhancements. Hence, we have used heuristic evaluation in our case study, we have made some scenarios. We have identified news apps that can run on the web and mobile platform. The apps were chosen based on the common usage. However, we have created our app to evaluate accessibility as well. We have contacted each of the members separately and gathered data from their app usage.

3.3.3 Data analysis procedure. While analyzing accessibility on mobile and web platforms, three experts were included in the evaluation and analysis of results. While conducting case study, we used Nielsen’s heuristic evaluation with its steps. We have already defined apps and target group. For the evaluation, we wanted from our users to evaluate PWAs in web and mobile platforms. Beforehand, we designed our app which is News4Elderly step-by-step based on WCAG 2.2 standards to make the app more accessible. While evaluation, three experts who have proficiency in UX/UI and accessibility participated in our research. Each application was analyzed properly and based on some research articles; the severity levels were identified for WCAG accessibility principles.

3.3.4 Reliability and Validity. For ensuring reliability and validity of our thesis, several measures were taken. For reliability and validity of our research, we undoubtedly designed our data methodology. To ensure reliability inter-rater reliability was used that we attracted multiple UX experts for addressing accessibility issues for elderly with low vision in web and mobile. Each of the experts gave us inspiration for conducting heuristic evaluation. We have made a conversation with each of the UX experts to get information about their years of experience that they have. All of the experts have knowledge about usability, and accessibility as well. Feedback have taken by note taking with previewing prototypes and last version of apps for our app.

For ensuring validity of our study, content validity used that evaluation criteria and suggestions used both in heuristic and accessibility evaluation by using WCAG principles. Hence, accessibility is our main priority, acceptance levels and principles were emphasized while conducting the thesis with references. In terms of accessibility evaluation, users and experts are involved to explore barriers. Additionally, task assignments were conducted to ensure usability and accessibility. We have gathered data from various kinds of apps, including our app as well. We got verbal agreement from our participants and the purpose of this research has already been discussed. Each of the members' data has been properly collected with our data methodology. Due to principles and guidelines are new for elderly people, we made those principles clear to our participants. For creating an accessible app, feedbacks were collected from experts based on prototypes.

Chapter 4

Findings

In this section we will give broad information about what we have found in methodology. We will discuss about findings based on our research. During evaluation, we have collected data from our specific target group, and we will describe them in each table. As a heuristic evaluation target group and apps were chosen. Second step is defining scenarios to drive case study by using heuristic evaluation. In last steps, records need to be analyzed and suggestions for enhancements must be provided based on these records.

These findings are more related to heuristic evaluation in case study. Our second goal is combining heuristic evaluation and accessibility evaluation that requires user and expert involvement in development phase. Therefore, we created our brand-new app to enhance accessibility in web and mobile. Until now, most of the research focused on either heuristic or accessibility evaluation separately. However, in our research, we wanted to present an innovation in accessibility.

Table 8

Participant with Their Commonly Used Applications, Environments, and Languages

Participant	Used desktop platform	Used mobile platform	Language preferences	Used Accessibility tool(s) for desktop	Used Accessibility tool(s) for mobile
P1	Windows	Apple	Azerbaijani, Turkish & Russian	JAWS	VoiceOver
P2	Windows	Android	Azerbaijani & Russian	NVDA, Magnifier	Talkback
P3	Windows	Android	Azerbaijani, Turkish & Russian	NVDA, Magnifier	Talkback
P4	Windows	Apple	Azerbaijani, Turkish & Russian	NVDA	VoiceOver
P5	Windows	Android	Azerbaijani & Russian	NVDA	Talkback
P6	Windows	Android	Azerbaijani & Russian	NVDA	Talkback

In table 8, we identified which randomly selected app or apps that they use in which environment. Language preferences are also mentioned. Accessibility tools for web and mobile, which have been consumed by elderly emphasized.

Table 9

Scenarios for PWAs in Web and Mobile Platform.

Scenarios
Navigate between pages
Using tooltips
Text resizing
Downloading the app
Using inputs/buttons

In table 9, we have defined scenarios for evaluating apps, specifically our app to enhance the accessibility in web and mobile platforms. Tasks are quite straightforward to understand in perspective of elderly.

Table 10

General Outcome of the Finished Assignments in Web Platform.

	Assignments					Completed tasks
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	
Participants						
P1	Done	Done	Done	Done	Done	5
P2	Done	Undone	Done	Undone	Done	3
P3	Done	Done	Done	Undone	Done	4
P4	Done	Done	Done	Undone	Done	4
P5	Done	Undone	Done	Undone	Done	3
P6	Done	Undone	Done	Undone	Done	3

In table 10, we have collected data from each participant about their assignment completion. Each of them used the apps in web platform.

Table 11

Times Used While Completing Tasks in Web Platform

Participants	Used time (sec)					Total (sec)
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	
P1	15	10	6	16	5	52
P2	20	0	15	0	9	44
P3	18	26	9	0	8	61
P4	20	30	13	0	7	70
P5	29	0	10	0	10	49
P6	23	0	16	0	10	49

Table 12

General Outcome of the Finished Assignments in Mobile Platform

	Assignments					Completed tasks
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	
Participants						
P1	Done	Done	Done	Done	Done	5
P2	Done	Undone	Done	Done	Done	4
P3	Done	Undone	Done	Done	Done	4
P4	Done	Done	Done	Done	Done	5
P5	Done	Undone	Done	Done	Done	4
P6	Done	Undone	Done	Done	Done	4

In table 12, participants again performed task in mobile platform.

Table 13

Times Used While Completing Tasks in Mobile Platform

Participants	Used time (sec)					Total (sec)
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	
P1	13	8	6	20	4	51
P2	23	0	12	30	8	73
P3	16	0	9	45	7	77
P4	18	40	11	38	6	113
P5	26	0	9	42	7	84
P6	20	0	13	50	9	92

The severity levels were adopted from various kinds of research for accessibility and usability evaluation, such as (Galkute, Rojas, & Sagal, 2020), (Alcaraz, Ribera, & Granollers, 2021), (Taieb-Maimon & Vaisman-Fairstein, 2022), (Zaina, Fortes,

Casadei, & Nozaki, 2022) and (Roumeliotis & Tselikas, 2022). We have identified numbers to each of the severity levels to make it human readable:

- 1 = Trivial
- 2 = Substantial
- 3 = Serious

Table 14

Identified Barriers of Apps with Heuristic Evaluation in Web Platform

Barriers	BBC News Azerbaijan	Metbuat	Oxu	News4Elderly
Types				
Contrast	1	1	1	1
Contrast adjustment	3	3	3	1
Text-to-speech	3	3	3	2
Consistent navigation	1	2	2	1
Resizing text	3	1	1	1
Identify aim	3	3	3	1
Heading and Labels	1	1	1	1
Tooltips	3	3	3	2
Abundance of images	2	3	2	1
Abundance of links	1	2	1	1
Keyboard	1	1	1	1
Language of pages	1	1	1	1
Language control	2	3	2	1

In table 14, we have gathered barriers of selected apps that have been consumed by elderly people in web platform.

Table 15

Identified Barriers of Apps with Heuristic Evaluation in Mobile Platform

Barriers	BBC News Azerbaijan	Metbuat	Oxu	News4Elderly
Types				
Contrast	1	1	1	1
Contrast adjustment	3	3	3	1
Text-to- speech	3	3	3	2
Consistent navigation	1	2	2	1
Resizing text	2	1	1	1
Identify aim	2	3	3	1
Heading and Labels	1	1	1	1
Tooltips	3	3	3	2
Abundance of images	2	3	2	1
Abundance of links	1	2	1	1
Keyboard	1	1	1	1
Language of pages	1	1	1	1
Language control	2	3	2	1

In table 15, we have gathered barriers of selected apps that have been consumed by elderly people in web platform.

Figure 6: Web prototype of our app before expert involvement.

Figure 7: Mobile prototype of our app before expert involvement.

In figures 6 and 7, prototypes of News4Elderly were created without any UX experts' involvement. However, for accessibility evaluation, we involved UX experts in development phase. Therefore, we got crucial feedback toward our app, then, we implemented them into our project. We have crucial feedback for our app to enhance accessibility and suggest proper solution towards accessibility.

Table 16

Suggestion from UX Experts for Our App

Experts	Suggestions			
UXE1	Add white border to mode change button	Adding padding to buttons	Adding icons to zoom buttons	Purpose of links and buttons
UXE2	Adding text-to-speech	Adding language controller		
UXE3	Contrast controller	Adding footer and navbar	Install button	Small guideline for how to use the app

Table 17

Information About UX Experts

Experts	Years of experience	Knowledge	Knowledge about platforms
UXE1	10	Usability and accessibility	Web and mobile
UXE2	7.5	Usability and accessibility	Web and mobile
UXE3	8	Usability and accessibility	Web and mobile

Each suggestion represents principles of WCAG guidelines to enhance accessibility and usability in any app, in our case News4Elderly. The app itself was created after evaluation of rest of the app. The reason behind this is understanding barriers and errors and suggesting possible treatment. After adding these suggestions, the last version of the app became like this:

Figure 8: Last version of our app on web.

Figure 9: Last version of our app on mobile.

As a conclusion for this chapter, we have collected possible information from our target group and UX experts.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion of Findings for Research Questions

In this section, we will discuss of findings about our research. We will show analyzes of heuristic and accessibility evaluation methods. These findings show both barriers and their violation level.

Based on first research question, we talked lot about evaluation techniques, such as heuristic evaluation, cognitive walkthrough, user centered design, and specifically accessibility evaluation. Various kinds of research have already been done by using one of these. We used heuristic evaluation with accessibility evaluation method as a combination to enhance accessibility. For the second question, we have explored barriers for elderly with low vision, and most of the violation occurs in perceivable, operable, and understandable principles. While conducting our research, we have ensured which barriers commonly occur. For the third one, we have investigated main guidelines for web and mobile accessibility. The most important guideline is WCAG guideline that covers both mobile and web. Additionally, various kinds of guidelines UUAG and ATAG explained as well. For the last question, we analyzed research articles, which use numerous kinds of evaluation methods. The most common methods were heuristic evaluation, user and expert involvement and automation tools.

Regarding the data from table 14, severity levels of apps are approximately 50 percent trivial, 18 percent substantial and 32 percent serious types in web environment. The most violated accessibility principles are perceivable with 30 percent, operable with 36 percent, understandable 22 percent and robust with 18 percent.

Regarding the data from table 15, severity levels of apps are approximately 50 percent trivial, 27 percent substantial and 23 percent serious types in mobile environment. The most violated accessibility principles are perceivable with 29 percent, operable with 29 percent, understandable 22 percent and robust with 20 percent.

Additionally, tables 11 and 13 represent the usability of those apps, which affects productivity of accessibility. Average of total completion time of apps on the web is 54 seconds, and for mobile platform is 82 seconds.

For suggesting proper solutions for these kinds of violation that are represented in table 14 and 15, we produced possible solutions for both web and mobile platforms. In table 16, we have collected feedback for our app. Additionally, we have identified personal information about UX experts in table 17.

Table 18

Solutions for Accessibility Violations Occur in Web and Mobile.

WCAG 2.2 principles	Success criterion (minimum)	Violations	Solutions
Perceivable 1.4	AA	Contrast adjustment	To have a controller to change contrast
Perceivable 1.4.2	AA	Text-to-speech control	Adding more comprehensive text-to-speech functions to enhance productivity of visual impairments
Perceivable 1.3	AA	Input purposes	Informative guidelines should dedicate
Operable 2.4.9	AAA	Link purpose	Informative text should dedicate
Understandable 3.3	AA	Tooltips aid	Activating tooltips with hover or focusing can be effective in terms of understanding visual elements
Perceivable 1.4	AA	Abundance of images	Using only functional images
Understandable 3.1.2	AA	Language control	Adding language controller should enhance understandability
Robust 4.1.2	A	Values and their roles	In programming perspective, inputs, links, and other elements should defined properly to render user interface components

Color contrast at least should be 4.5:1 ratio contrast based on WCAG 2.2 AA level. Additionally, based on the WCAG 2.1 and 2.2 guidelines, font size should be 18 pixels at least, but 20 pixels is preferable. Line height must be 1.5 pixels based on visual presentation of WCAG perceivable 1.4.8. According to the research of Beier, Oderkerk, Bay and Larsen (2021), font weight does not matter for low vision people, but font size as a Times New Romans is more readable font for them. HTML elements define with values and roles, such as buttons, inputs, and links. Defining roles, values, and their purposes improves performance of rendered elements. Images can be different based on their aim, therefore, images must be set properly, whether it is functional or representative. Defining language of content and controlling it enhance accessibility so that a user will not need any additional tools to manage it. Audio controllers are main components for elderly with visual impairments.

5.2 Conclusion

Accessibility is an important aspect in terms of people with disabilities, specifically for older adults. There are lots of interests that we must be aware of, such as health care, social activity, advertisement, etc. In this research, we have conducted research that is related to news, because most of the elderly people get latest information about the world from news. They need to get information about what happens around the world. Sometimes they feel awkward about learning new things with a recent technology with deficiency of accessibility. Therefore, humanity must be responsive of accessibility for software, applications, and technologies. Based on most of the research, and including our one, older people inform us that they would use modern technologies, if it were comfortable to consume. They seek that technologies should be accessible and user-friendly.

In our research, we have collected information about the most common barriers and accessibility violations that occur in terms of elderly with low vision. Furthermore, we got deeper knowledge about accessibility by exploring HCI, UX and UCD. We have analyzed some apps with heuristic and accessibility evaluation techniques. We suggested enhancements towards those barriers, such as text and image resizing, keyboard navigation, big screens, buttons, font size and images, controlling color contrast, text-to-speech functionality, link, and input purposes. However, those violations had to be solved during the development phase. Most of the violations occur in perceivable, understandable, and operable. Workable solutions were presented, and

those improvements should obey at least AA level of success creation. All these principles and violations are backbone of accessibility. However, it is not sufficient to evaluate accessibility. The best approach is combining various kinds of evaluation methods with user centered design. With this approach, it is applicable to enhance accessibility, because there are lots of cases in terms of disabilities.

Accessibility should not be the last step of software applications. Violations should be solved during development period and possible accessibility tools should be implemented in apps.

5.3 Limitations

Through our research procedures, lots of research articles were analyzed and implemented about accessibility in web and mobile platforms. Therefore, we have already seen some limitations in that research. According to our research, there are various kinds of limitations that we can list. First, even though we have declared specific target group, applications do not cover all the accessibility probabilities in terms of physical, cognitive, vision etc. Each application should address all accessibility issues, but this is not possible. Generally, applications do not cover all the possibilities of accessibility and usability. Additionally, we should reach out to more elderly people all over the world to understand the importance of accessibility.

Secondly, WCAG principles are not perfect solutions for accessibility issues. According to the some research such as Roumeliotis and Tselikas (2022), Potluri, Grindeland, Froehlich and Mankoff (2021), WCAG principles are arduous and hard to implement for newbies in the accessibility technologies related applications. Many UX and UI experts lack accessibility practice, therefore, it is important to acquire WCAG principles and implement them properly.

Thirdly, applications are being used by users and they would feel different towards applications usage. So, it is hard to understand all scenarios about usage from the perspective of people who have disabilities. Hence, our target groups consist of elderly, it is hard to understand some deep concepts of accessibility and its evaluation principles. While creating our app, it was hard to get plausible and positive feedback from them. Therefore, while prototyping, we have got feedback from UX experts.

Fourthly, even though some accessibility tools were added, text-to-speech functionality was not efficient in terms of language selection, and only limited number of languages are supported.

5.4 Recommendations for Future Research

In our research, we combined heuristic evaluation with accessibility evaluation, which expert and user involvement implemented, that considers about usability and accessibility, respectively. In the future, it is suggested to combine cognitive walkthrough with these methods. Besides this, it is important to add automation evaluation tools to improve accessibility of any apps.

Also, it is preferable that reaching out more people with diverse backgrounds and various kinds of disabilities to solve accessibility from all over the world. Contacting more elderly people with different customs can give us broad understanding and more strength to conduct research for accessibility. Additionally, combining user centered design principles can be greatly beneficial to progress accessibility. While creating our app, we get feedback from our user, even though it was hard to get positive and plausible response. However, complete UCD procedure needs more work, and it is important to get in touch with knowledgeable UX experts and end users to enhance accessibility.

Although we added some accessibility tools, we will work on these tools to improve productivity, by doing this, there will not be any need for additional tools.

REFERENCES

- Acosta-Vargas, P., Salvador-Acosta, B., Zalakeviciute, R., & Alexandrino, K. (2020). Accessibility Assessment of Mobile Meteorological Applications for Users with Low Vision. *Advances in Human Factors and Systems Interaction*, 1-7. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-51369-6_27
- Acosta-Vargas, P., Salvador-Ullauri, L., Perez, J., & Zalakeviciute, R. (2020). Heuristic Method of Evaluating Accessibility of Mobile in Selected Applications for Air Quality Monitoring. *In book: Advances in Human Factors and Systems Interaction*, 485-495. doi:DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-20040-4_44
- Aela Design and Training. (2022, 12 14). *Topics: Nielsen's Heuristics: 10 Usability Principles To Improve UI Design*. Retrieved from Aela School Web site: <https://aelaschool.com/en/interactiondesign/10-usability-heuristics-ui-design/#:~:text=Nielsen's%20heuristics%20are%20general%20principles,friendly%2C%20and%20intuitive%20digital%20products>.
- Alajarmeh, N. (2021). Non-visual access to mobile devices: A survey of touchscreen accessibility for users who are visually impaired. *Displays*, 70, 1-18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.displa.2021.102081>
- Alcaraz, R., Ribera, M., & Granollers, T. (2021). Methodology for heuristic evaluation of the accessibility of statistical charts for people with low vision and color vision deficiency. *Heuristics*, 1-34. doi:<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-156959/v1>
- Beier, S., Oderkerk, C., Bay, B., & Larsen, M. (2021). Increased letter spacing and greater letter width improve reading acuity in low vision readers. *Information Design Journal*, 26(1), 73-88. doi:doi.org/10.1075/idj.19033.bei
- Bi, T., Xia, X., Lo, D., Grundy, J., Zimmermann, T., & Ford, D. (2022). Accessibility in Software Practice: A Practitioner's Perspective. *ACM Transactions on*

Software Engineering and Methodology, 31(4), 1-26.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3503508>

Borthwick, M., Tomitsch, M., & Gaughwin, M. (2022). From human-centred to life-centred design: Considering environmental and ethical concerns in the design of interactive products. *Journal of Responsible Technology*, 10, 1-10. doi:10.1016/j.jrt.2022.100032

Brdnik, S., Hericko, T., & Sumak, B. (2022). Intelligent User Interfaces and Their Evaluation: A Systematic Mapping Study. *Sensors: AI-Enabled Sensing Technology and Data Analysis Techniques for Intelligent Human-Computer Interaction*, 1-36. doi:10.3390/s22155830

Bruun, A., Nielsen, L., Larusdottir, M., Nielse, P. A., & Perrson, J. S. (2018). The role of UX professionals in agile development: a case study from industry. *NordiCHI'18* (pp. 1-10). Oslo: ACM. doi:10.1145/3240167.3240213

Cajander, A., Larusdottir, M., & Geiser, J. L. (2022). UX professionals' learning and usage of UX methods in agile. *Information and Software Technology*, 151, 1-9. doi:10.1016/j.infsof.2022.107005

Campoverde-Molina, M., Lujan-Mora, S., & Garcia, L. (2020). Empirical Studies on Web Accessibility of Educational Websites: A Systematic Literature Review. *IEEE Xplore*, 8, 91676-91700. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2994288

Dias, J., Carvalho, D., Rocha, T., & Barroso, J. (2022). Automated Evaluation Tools for Web and Mobile Accessibility: proposal of a new adaptive interface. *International Conference on Industry Science and Computer Science Innovation*, 204, 297-304. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.08.036>

Ferati, M., & Vogel, B. (2020). Accessibility in Web Development Courses: A Case Study. *Informatics*(7), 1-15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics7010008>

Filipe, F., Pires, I., & Gouveia, A. (2023). Why Web Accessibility Is Important for Your Institution. *Procedia Computer Science*, 219, 20-27. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.01.259>

- Gaggi, O., & Perinello, L. (2022). Improving accessibility of web accessibility rules. *GoodIT 2022: ACM International Conference on Information Technology for Social Good* (pp. 167-174). Limassol, Cyprus: Association for Computing Machinery. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3524458.3547267>
- Galkute, M., Rojas, L., & Sagal, V. (2020). Improving the Web Accessibility of a University Library for People with Visual Disabilities Through a Mixed Evaluation Approach. *HCII 2020* (pp. 56-71). Switzerland: Springer, Cham. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49570-1_5
- Geiser, J. L. (2020). *How do UX Professionals Apply UX Methods and Practice Lifelong Learning?* Uppsala University, Department of Informatics and Media. Uppsala: Uppsala University. Retrieved from <http://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1448758&dswid=-2704>
- Giovanna, B., Manca, M., Paterno, F., & Pulina, F. (2020). Flexible Automatic Support for Web Accessibility Validation. *Systems and tools for interaction design; User Interface toolkits, 4*, 1-24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3397871>
- Iancu, I., & Iancu, B. (2020). Designing mobile technology for elderly. A theoretical overview. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 1-9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.119977>
- Inal, Y., Guribye, F., Rajanen, D., Rajanen, M., & Rost, M. (2020). Perspectives and Practices of Digital Accessibility: A Survey of User Experience Professionals in Nordic Countries. *Proceedings of the 11th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction: Shaping Experiences, Shaping Society* (pp. 1-11). Tallinn: NordiCHI '20. doi:<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3419249.3420119>
- Ismail, A., & Kuppusamy, K. (2019). Web accessibility investigation and identification of major issues of higher education websites with statistical measures: A case study of college websites. *Journal of King Saud University –Computer and Information Sciences*, 34(3), 901-911. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2019.03.011>

- Ismailova, R., & Inal, Y. (2022). Comparison of Online Accessibility Evaluation Tools: An Analysis of Tool Effectiveness. *in IEEE Access*, 10, 58233 - 58239. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3179375
- ISO 9241-210:2019. (2022, 11 21). *ISO 9241-210:2019(en) Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems*. Retrieved from Online Browsing Platform - ISO: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:9241:-210:ed-2:v1:en>
- Kashfi, P., Feldt, R., & Nilsson, A. (2019). Integrating UX principles and practices into software development organization: A case study of influencing events. *The Journal of Systems and Software*, 154, 37-58. doi:10.1016/j.jss.2019.03.066
- King, M. L. (1963, August). The Negro Is Your Brother. *The Atlantic Monthly*, 212, 78-88. The Atlantic Monthly.
- Knight, W. (2019). *UX for Developers: How to Integrate User-Centered Design Principles Into Your Day-to-Day Development Work*. Northampton, UK: Apress Media LLC. doi:10.1007/978-1-4842-4227-8
- Królak, A., & Zajac, P. (2022). Analysis of the accessibility of selected massive open online courses (MOOCs) for users with disabilities. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 1-12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-022-00927-2>
- Kuppusamy, K., & Balaji, V. (2021). Evaluating web accessibility of educational institutions websites using a variable magnitude approach. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 241-250. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-021-00812-4>
- Leite, M., Scatalon, L., Freire, A., & Eler, M. (2021). Accessibility in the mobile development industry in Brazil: Awareness, knowledge, adoption, motivations and barriers. *The Journal of Systems & Software*, 177, 1-25. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2021.110942>

- Lin, C., & Ho, S.-H. (2020). The development of a mobile user interface ability evaluation system for the elderly. *Applied Ergonomics*, 89, 1-19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2020.103215>
- Mateus, D., Silva, C., Oliveira, A., Costa, H., & Freire, A. (2021). A Systematic Mapping of Accessibility Problems Encountered on Websites and Mobile Apps: A Comparison Between Automated Tests, Manual Inspections and User Evaluations. *SBC Journal on Interactive Systems*, 1-27. doi:[10.5753/jis.2021.1778](https://doi.org/10.5753/jis.2021.1778)
- Meurer, J., Stein, M., Randall, D., & Wulf, V. (2018). Designing for way-finding as practices –A study of elderly people’s mobility. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 115, 40-51. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2018.01.008>
- Miranda, D. G., & Araujo, J. (2020). A Framework for Integrating Web Accessibility Requirements in Agile Methodologies. *CEUR Workshop*. 2822, pp. 1-10. Lisboa: CEUR Workshop Proceedings. Retrieved from <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2822/p5.pdf>
- Nuñez, A., Moquillaza, A., & Paz, F. (2019). Web Accessibility Evaluation Methods: A Systematic Review. *in Design, User Experience, and Usability. Practice and Case Studies*, 226-237. doi:[10.1007/978-3-030-23535-2_17](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-23535-2_17)
- Paiva, D., Freire, A., & Fortes, R. (2021). Accessibility and Software Engineering Processes: A Systematic Literature Review. *The Journal of Systems & Software*, 1-17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2020.110819>
- Park, K., So, H.-J., & Cha, H. (2019). Digital equity and accessible MOOCs: Accessibility evaluations of mobile MOOCs for learners with visual impairments. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 35, 48-63. doi:<https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.5521>
- Pelzetter, J. (2021). A Declarative Model for Web Accessibility Requirements and its Implementation. *Human-Media Interaction*, 3. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomp.2021.605772>

- Pichiliani, T., & Pizzolato, E. (2021). Cognitive disabilities and web accessibility: a survey into the Brazilian web development community. *Journal on Interactive Systems*, 1-19. doi:10.5753/jis.2021.982
- Potluri, V., Grindeland, T., Froehlich, J., & Mankoff, J. (2021). Examining Visual Semantic Understanding in Blind and Low-Vision Technology Users. *CHI '21: Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1-14. doi:https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445040
- Roumeliotis, K., & Tselikas, N. (2022). Evaluating Progressive Web App Accessibility for People with Disabilities. *MDPI: network*, 2, 350-369. doi:https://doi.org/10.3390/network2020022
- Sharp, H., Rogers, Y., & Preece, J. (2019). *Interaction Design: beyond human-computer interaction, Fifth Edition* (5th ed.). Indianapolis, Indiana, United States of America: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Shu, Y., Xiong, C., & Fan, S. (2020). Interactive design of intelligent machine vision based on human-computer interaction mode. *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, 75, 1-5. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103059
- Szabo, B., & Hercegfi, K. (2022). User-centered approaches in software development processes: Qualitative research into the practice of Hungarian companies. *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process*, 1-28. doi:10.1002/smr.2501
- Taieb-Maimon, M., & Vaisman-Fairstein, E. (2022). Improving older adults' accessibility to the web using real-time online interactive guides. *International Journal of Human - Computer Studies*, 164, 1-20. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2022.102830
- Travis, D., & Hodgson, P. (2022). *Think Like a UX Researcher: How to Observe Users, Influence Design, and Shape Business Strategy*. Boca Raton, Florida, United States of America: CRC Press.
- Trukenbrod, A., Backhaus, N., & Thomaschke, R. (2020). Measuring subjectively experienced time in usability and user experiencetesting scenarios.

International Journal of Human-Computer Studies, 138, 1-14.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2020.102399>

Usability.gov. (2022, 10 07). *Home: What & Why of Usability: User Experience Basics*. Retrieved from usability.gov: <https://www.usability.gov/what-and-why/user-experience.html>

Vishwarupe, V., Maheshwari, S., Deshmukh, A., Mhaisalkar, S., Joshi, P., & Mathias, N. (2022). Bringing Humans at the Epicenter of Artificial Intelligence: A Confluence of AI, HCI and Human Centered Computing. *International Conference on Industry Sciences and Computer Science Innovation*, 1-8.
doi:10.1016/j.procs.2022.08.111

Vollenwyder, B., Opwis, K., & Brühlmann, F. (2020). How Web Professionals Perceive Web Accessibility in Practice: Active Roles, Process Phases and Key Disabilities. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science book series*, 12376, 294-302.
doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58796-3_35

W3C. (2022, 1 18). *What's New in WCAG 2.2 Draft*. Retrieved from W3C: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/new-in-22/#:~:text=Changes%20from%20WCAG%202.1%20to%20WCAG%202.2,-All%20success%20criteria&text=The%202.0%20and%202.1%20success,suc cess%20criteria%20from%20WCAG%202.1.>

W3C. (2023, May 20). *Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2*. Retrieved from W3C: <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG22/>

World Health Organization. (2021, 11 24). *Disability and health: WHO*. Retrieved 2022, from World Health Organization (WHO): <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/disability-and-health>

Yang, H.-L., & Lin, S.-L. (2019). The reasons why elderly mobile users adopt ubiquitous mobile social service. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 93, 62-75.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.12.005>

- Zaina, L., Fortes, R., Casadei, V., & Nozaki, L. P. (2022). Preventing accessibility barriers: Guidelines for using user interface design patterns in mobile applications. *The Journal of Systems & Software*, 186, 1-26. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2021.111213>
- Zardari, B. A., Hussain, Z., Arain, A. A., Rizvi, W. W., & Vighio, M. S. (2021). Development and Validation of User Experience-Based E-Learning Acceptance Model for Sustainable Higher Education. *Visual Technologies for Sustainable Digital Environments*, 1-17. doi:10.3390/su13116201
- Zhang, X., Greef, L., Swearngin, A., White, S., Murray, K., Yu, L., . . . Bigham, J. (2021). Screen Recognition: Creating Accessibility Metadata for Mobile Applications from Pixels. *CHI on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1-15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445186>